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PROYECTO DÍNAMO: DESIGNERS EXPLORING THE POSSIBILITIES OF SHOOTERS AS ACTIVE GAMES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the current status of a project involving a modification of the user experience of an existing shooting action video game to explore this genre's possibilities as new scenarios for physical activity. A prototype in development serves as a tool by conditioning the functionality of the game controllers to the alternated movement of the legs the player has to perform. Upon reaching a defined speed ("walk"), the device enables the component controlling advance and, upon reaching a defined a higher value, the one controlling the "run" function transforming a shooting game into a shooting themed active game.

Keywords: user experience, active gaming, exergaming, games, video games, tangible user interfaces, controllers

INTRODUCTION

Exergaming defined as videogames serving as means for capturing people's attention, maintaining their interest and effectively making them perform physical activity (Görgü et al., 2010) has become the field of work for many researchers around the world. For many years now, connecting exercise and videogames has grown from being a key element for making human-computer interactions richer (Ishii-1999) to a whole new way of creating a better future in the form of healthier lifestyles. Kili & Merilampi (2010) and Sinclair et al. (2007) have developed *exergames* of their own. Sinclair et al. (2007) also provide a proper framework and method for the development of these kinds of experiences. A common motivation for these studies and developments is the concern about increased child and teen obesity derived from extended physical inactivity and the connections of these problems

with gaming. The video game industry has been sensitive to the situation, too: in recent times, innovative gaming products frequently emerge as promising efforts towards the promotion of physical activity. Titles like *Wii Fit* (Published: Nintendo, 2008), *Active Life Outdoor Challenge* (Published: Namco Bandai Games, 2008), *EA Sports Active* (Published: Electronic Arts, 2009), and *Zumba Fitness* (Published: Majesco, 2010) released in the last few years make it possible to exercise at home using an entertainment computer system. Most of these titles are sold bundled with special controllers or accessories that allow the player to enjoy all the benefits the physical experience. These games that emulate the gym and the personal trainer, the dance floor and even outdoor activity have proven to be effective motivating a wide audience and making them rethink their everyday lives and adopt healthier habits.

Even though exergaming has become popular recently, it has roots in the past. A pioneer of active gaming is the *Dance Dance Revolution* (DDR) series by Konami. These games, originally designed for the arcade, are operated with a controller located on the floor with pressure sensitive pads identified with arrows pointing forward, backwards, left and right. On the screen, as a song plays, a sequence of arrows pointing in different directions scroll up and, as they reach a limit, the player is expected to step on the corresponding arrow in the pad. The more precision and the longer the sequence the player is able to perform correctly, the higher the score. The DDR franchise is usually classified under the rhythm/puzzle category but it is unquestionable these games constitute proper workout. Active games based on activities such as dancing, jogging, and stretching have reached a considerable level of sophistication thanks to the introduction of

the concept of motion sensing into console gaming. Without underestimating the relevance of the Samba de Amigo maracas controller for the arcade and Dreamcast console (Sega, 1999, 2000) or the Eye Toy camera for the Playstation 2 console (Sony, 2003), the release of the Nintendo Wii console in 2006 and its subsequent commercial success represents motion based gaming becoming a mainstream phenomenon. The idea of controlling videogames with the natural movements of the body instead of having to spend time learning a long list of functions and buttons made this platform appealing to the casual gamer. The other two major actors in the video game console business later presented their approaches to a more intuitive interaction paradigm. In 2010, Sony released the Move controller for the PlayStation 3 system and Microsoft introduced the Kinect sensor for the Xbox 360 console as alternatives to their own respective traditional gamepads.

Motion sensing has opened possibilities in terms of the complexity of movements and the number of body parts that can be used to control an active game:

The progress from stepping with the legs on a floor pad in the original *Dance Dance Revolution* (Publisher: Konami, Japan, 1998) or *Active Life Outdoor Challenge* (Published: Namco Bandai Games, 2008), to moving controllers in *Wii Sports* (Publisher: Nintendo, 2006) or *Just Dance* (Published: Ubisoft, 2009) to moving controllers plus balancing the body on the balance board in titles like *Wii Fit* (Published: Nintendo, 2008), *Don King Boxing* (Publisher: 2K Sports, 2009) or *Dance Dance Revolution Hottest Party 3* (Publisher: Konami, Japan, 2009) to full body involvement and control through Kinect in *Dance Central* (Publisher: Microsoft, 2010) is a demonstration of this.

The next challenge should be about how to translate these physically rich forms of interaction and the benefits of exergaming to players who prefer other videogame genres. There is one possible answer in what makes commercial active games distinct: controllers. This is clear for commercial active games but not necessarily for other kinds of games. One genre that, when accessorized, suggests physical action or, at least, full body immersion is shooters. Like the rough evolution line mentioned before for active games, shooters with special controllers have

a history. Reminiscent of shooting galleries in parks and fairs, the light-gun controller and the Duck Hunt game originally bundled with the Nintendo Entertainment System NES (1985) are a start point. A next step is arcade on-rails shooters designed to be played using a light-gun like *Area 51* (Publisher: Atari, 1995), *Time Crisis* (Publisher: Namco, 1995) and *House of the Dead* (Publisher: Sega, 1996).

The light-gun never really left the scene: the original GunCon controller was bundled with the PlayStation port of *Time Crisis* (Publisher: Namco, 1997) and the light-gun concept appears on the Wii in the form of the Wii Zapper, a gun-like accessory that has two cradles, one for the Wii remote placed like the cannon, and one for the nunchuck - the Wii console secondary navigation controller -, placed over the handle. Some on-rails shooters released for the Wii are *Resident Evil: the Umbrella Chronicles* (Publisher: Capcom, 2007), *Ghost Squad* (Publisher: Sega, 2008), *House of the Dead 2 & 3 Return* (Publisher: Sega, 2008), *House of the Dead: Overkill* (Publisher: Sega, 2009), and *Resident Evil: The Dark Side Chronicles* (Publisher: Capcom, 2009).

The Wii Zapper is not only used with on-rails shooters; it is also an option for first person shooters like *Medal of Honor 2: Heroes* (Publisher: Electronic Arts, 2007), *Call of Duty: World at War* (Publisher: Activision, 2008), *Call of Duty: Modern Warfare: Reflex Edition* (Publisher: Activision, 2009) and *Goldeneye 007* (Publisher: Activision, 2010).

Posture and gesture provide the player with a feeling of immersion into the game but physical activity in shooters does not go any further than *point and shoot*. Does including well-integrated physical activity to shooting games constitute a way to introduce workout alternatives able to retain the interest and eventually help building a routine for these other numerous video game players?

Proyecto Dinamo follows an experimental approach to transform already existing shooting gameplay experiences into shooting action themed active gaming experiences that will serve as reference scenarios towards videogame innovations in the future.

PROCESS

Proyecto Dinamo began as a design project with the sole idea of observing the effect of including an

accessory controller that conditioned the operation of the advance / speed functions of the control scheme in a shooting action videogame to the actions of walking / running performed by the player, considering the game as a “ready-made” virtual environment for entertainment and workout. In order to define the configuration of the device, the initial approach was to directly apply an existing physically demanding form of interaction used in other videogames.

An empirical process consisting of iterative prototype development and user testing - progressing from a low fidelity until a high fidelity solution (Rudd, J. et al. 1996)- is achieved and validated is being applied. For being the only platform by the beginning of the project having motion sensing as the main control system, the Nintendo Wii was selected.

Figure 1. WiiFit “Marathon” mode (original) gameplay sessions as edited for video analysis. Left: body-space-controller-screen relation. Middle: screen only. Right: frontal shot of facial expression / body language.

Preliminary gameplay sessions using WiiFit (Published: Nintendo, 2008) (Figure 1) and *Dance Dance Revolution Hottest Party* (Publisher: Konami, 2007) (Figure 2) determined the latter constituted a more demanding kind of workout and led to the decision of using a dance mat accessory in a way similar to the one in *Winds of Orbis - an Active Adventure* (Carnegie Mellon University Entertainment Technology Center, USA, 2008) where physical activity in role play videogames was explored by controlling a character using a dance mat, a Wii remote and a nunchuck to interact with characters and the environment.

Figure 2. Dance Dance Revolution Hottest Party gameplay sessions in total body mode (dance mat + Wii remote + nunchuck) as edited for video analysis. Left: body-space-controller-screen relation. Middle: screen only. Right: frontal shot of facial expression / body language.

Additional sessions took place using Wii Fit in “Marathon” mode, a jogging activity performed by introducing the Wii remote in the pants pocket to sense movement with no use of the balance board. A modified dance mat - reduced to one single pad including two pressure sensors - was introduced to the setting and the players were instructed to perform the activity on it. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. WiiFit “Marathon” mode + modified dance mat gameplay schematics.

Participants were not told the modified dance mat did not have a function other than sending a test signal to a PC via a hacked USB keyboard circuit to be processed with a graphical analysis application written in *Processing*, a programming environment specially developed for artists and designers (<http://processing.org/>). Many players declared it was easy to lose track of the small mat and described the situation as “stressful” (Figure 4).

Figure 4. WiiFit "Marathon" mode + modified dance mat gameplay sessions as edited for video analysis. Left: body-space-controller-screen relation. Middle: screen only. Right: frontal shot of facial expression / body language.

This led to discard the concept of a mat to adopt that of a wearable device maintained until now. Having taken this decision, the team proceeded to develop a first version of a modified gameplay experience by introducing an accessory controller that conditioned the functionality of the joystick in the nunchuck - dedicated to control the advance ("walk") of the character in a game - to the alternated movement of the two legs read by sensors located directly on them. The functionality of the button controlling "run" was conditioned to the alternated movement of the legs at a higher-speed. A similar effort, the *Wii jog*, a commercial Wii accessory controller, was released in the United Kingdom in 2009 by New Concept Gaming. This device conditions the movement of the joystick in a nunchuck to movements detected by an electronic device similar to a pedometer placed on the hip or into the pockets of a Wii player. When the WiiOG is active and the player walks, the character in the game moves in the direction the joystick is pointing to.

Among the games that offered at the moment control schemes that met the requirements previously defined for the experiment, *Resident Evil 4 - Wii edition* (Capcom, 2007) was chosen for having a moderate pace, rich gameplay - ranging from slow exploration sequences to fast melee action and shooting scenes to puzzle solving -, a solid control system and an interesting story - in order to focus in the quality of interaction: Progressing from not deteriorating to maintaining to crafting a proper game experience involving a meaningful and novel

physical activity should allow evaluating, by contrast, if the player would prefer the original over the new one and, if so, he or she would like to come back to experiences of this new kind.

Stage I

Preliminary prototypes: foot pads with vibration and visual (light) feedback and tabletop two button auxiliary keyboard during control software development. (Figures 5, 6)

Figure 5. Preliminary prototypes schematics: foot pads and tabletop keyboard.

Figure 6. Preliminary prototypes: foot pads and tabletop keyboard as edited for video analysis. Top, left: tabletop keyboard. Bottom: foot pads. Top, right: Graphic pulsations counter.

The first functional wearable model included sensors (mercury switches replacing the function of the pads in the modified dance mat) attached to motocross shin protectors using the same electronics and software as the previous version. Hand crafted sensors presented limitations when capturing motion at the required speed (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Stage I functional prototype schematics.

Effects of the physical effort required to the players were described in ways like "feeling exhausted after playing just for a few seconds" because of the speed needed to activate character action and the gesture defined for the purpose (knee flexion). Limitations in the flow of the activity derived from the intermittent behavior of the controller. Experience quality was perceived as "too demanding" to the point in certain sessions, if there were more than two players, they would prefer sharing functions: one guiding and the other one exclusively running (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Stage I user testing sessions as edited for video analysis.

Stage II

For the next iteration an emphasis was put into providing the system with a proper identity and refining the functionality of the previous version in order to deliver a better experience quality. In relation to identity, a robust structure in textile materials was designed to give the player the feeling of being impersonating a fictional character via a military-looking form language while giving proper support and protection to the electronic components. In relation to functionality, it was a priority to centralize prototype components that, so

far, were dispersed and to design a more detailed control experience. Sensors were relocated from the shins to the thighs and secured in pockets included in bands with straps in the back. By the end of stage II mercury switches were replaced by three-axis accelerometers. A new device located in a belt, connected to the structures in the thighs, containing a central processing unit based on the Wiring mini input/output prototyping board was added (Figure 9). (<http://wiring.org.co/>)

Figure 9. Stage II: functional prototype parts schematics.

Figure 10. Stage II prototype: testing calibration sequence in the laboratory (2010).

This device also served as a connection hub from the sensors to the original controllers and to a PC running calibration and monitoring software. The calibration sequence was executed before playing the game. The player was instructed to walk and run for a few seconds to set values for the "walk" and "run" modes then control software was loaded via USB to the Wiring board (Figures 10, 11). A mechanical control wheel conceived to be placed in the lower part of the chest to modify the Dínamo system settings while playing was designed but never implemented.

Figure 11. Images from the calibration /monitoring program. Top: initializing. Middle: calibration. Bottom: monitoring.

By the end of this stage, general configuration of the system was defined as well as the system components, in general, except for batteries; due to schedule limitations, it was decided to continue obtaining power via USB. System functionality was tested with the monitoring software with positive results.

Stage III

Since Stage I, low level communication between the Dínamo accessory and the original Wii controllers was attempted unsuccessfully. As a consequence, for Stage III, this exploration was suspended and performing direct physical connections to the nunchuck internal electronics was decided. By the beginning of stage III, the prototype in general was functional although not completely robust. In order to guarantee the integrity of the electronic components, circuits were protected in acrylic boxes, and these, fixed to the textile structure (Figure 12). The prototype was able to remain functional for up to six hours before it stopped working most probably due to limitations in the controlling software; this, however, did not represent a problem for testing sessions that, in most cases, did not run for more than two hours. Setting and calibration on the PC during intermediate testing sessions took a relatively long time and started to have a negative impact on the testers' mood; to improve the flow of this sessions it was decided to include knobs on the central unit

frontal panel to adjust resistance and momentum values for both the "walk" and "run" modes as the action happened to avoid delays, interruptions and distractions. During this stage, efforts were aimed towards establishing a range of values enough to allow players to personalize their settings according to the "feel" they preferred to have whether this was a workout kind of experience (high resistance/low momentum) or a more relaxed one (lower resistance/high momentum) (Figure 13).

Figure 12. The Dínamo prototype during Stage III. Electronics in acrylic boxes attached to a textile support structure.

Figure 13. Wiring mini-powered central unit with adjustment knobs in frontal panel and peripheral sockets for input/output.

Lag between the player's actions and their representation on the screen was relatively low; it was even been described by guest players as giving "a natural feel of momentum" and not detrimental to the experience. This "feel of momentum", annoying to other players, originated the addition of a "brake" button to the nunchuck (to force-break the movement of the character) providing a good sense of control. Further testing lead to the inclusion of a "bypass" switch in the nunchuck, a feature the

WiiJOG included in its corresponding CPU, to allow the player to perform actions like *aiming a gun* or *managing inventory* that, do not and should not, require the player to be nonsensically *walking* or *running* (Figure 14).

Figure 14. A modified nunchuck controller. Notice thumb pressing the "brake" button and middle finger located on the "activate/bypass" switch in the ventral part of the controller.

These features, in addition to those developed previously, made the combination of a Wii remote, a nunchuck controller and complementary *Dinamo* accessory, usable. Now enabled to provide continuous gameplay support and a close to complete control scheme, the prototype was tested by users more formally not yet extensively (Figure 15).

Figure 15. *Dinamo* - Stage III- user testing sessions.

Experience sessions had nine participants of an average age of 25. Three of the participants were women and six, men. Guests were selected to match three different profiles: advanced gamer, basic gamer and casual / non-gamer, in order to give perspective to a detailed observation of the use of

the *Dinamo* prototype to integrate physical activity to the gameplay experience of *Resident Evil 4 - Wii Edition*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Although general response to the gameplay experience modified by the inclusion of the *Dinamo* prototype was positive in the form of perception of novelty value, which is somehow a demonstration of having the capacity to *create interest* in some videogame players, it is difficult at this point of the project, to have a final answer to the question if the *Dinamo* experience will certainly retain the players' interest or will create a workout habit around this particular form of interaction / experience.

The testers' disposition to try out the prototype and their openness at recounting their feelings, emotions and impressions was positive; so it was noticing that even though there were technical limitations in some aspects like disabled functions or modes that reduced the possibility of interacting in a completely transparent and deep way with the game, participants of the user experience sessions did not quit and declared they would repeat the experience - a hint around "retaining interest"- . Testing sessions in the laboratory not described in this paper allowed longer play times and the possibility of saving the game and play for several consecutive days advancing in the story and enjoying the *Dinamo* gameplay extensively; these players could provide an insight on "building a habit".

Probably, the most interesting finding is that of a different perception of time. Would it confirm the popular expression "time flies when you're having fun" in this particular context? How beneficial it would be losing the notion of time when immersed in a story that retains your interest for days and makes you workout without noticing it?

Latest efforts have been oriented to delivering a robust, stable, reliable and comfortable device that seamlessly (between the limits of what is possible) integrates with the existing game and maintains a smooth flow of the experience allowing to observe longer continuous gameplay sessions with the *Dinamo*. The team will continue to develop a streamlined version of the device with normalized electronics that will provide more information about the experience in the extended time.

This will also allow testing the Dínamo with other games. Experiments with First Person Shooters, such as the Goldeneye 007 remake for the Wii (Publisher: Activision, 2010) in campaign mode and split screen multiplayer or Medal of Honor 2: Heroes (Publisher: Electronic Arts, 2007) are being considered to be next on the schedule.

As what began as a design project demands for further research work to validate what so far are clues provided by direct observation of a reduced group of players, aligning the project with more solid, structured methods is the next logical step to formally continue in the path of design research. Having accomplished the goal of building a functional tool that should help evaluating the initial design hypothesis of including well-integrated physical activity components to shooting games as a way to introduce workout alternatives able to retain the interest and eventually help build a routine for video game players fond of action games, the empirical research through design method (ERDM) by Keyson and Bruns Alonso (2009) provides an interesting, clear structure that retains the original practice-driven orientation of the Dínamo project. As for elucidating the true factors behind the development of a workout habit around the extended practice of a specially designed active game experience, captology (Fogg, 1998) or the study of computers as persuasive technology and all the production built on this concept, should provide with quality methods and tools in relation to the introduction of new behaviors.

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NOTE: Videogames cited in this paper correspond to releases in the United States, Canada and Latin America.